

SECURITY SIMULATION OF WEB AUTHENTICATION: ANALYSIS OF BRUTE FORCE PAYLOAD USING ARGON2ID

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Abstract

This project explores web authentication vulnerabilities by running a dictionary brute-force attack against a custom Python Flask server. The original plaintext setup was highly vulnerable, letting an automated script guess hundreds of passwords a second by keeping a TCP connection alive. To fix this, I built a defense-in-depth architecture. Swapping the plaintext checks for the Argon2id algorithm forced a heavy computational workload that immediately broke the attack's speed. I also added an IP rate limiter as a network safeguard to drop connections after five failed logins. The practical results show that combining memory-hard cryptography with strict traffic cutoffs effectively mitigates automated credential attacks.

Keywords: *Web Authentication, Brute Force Simulation, Argon2id, Rate Limiting, Python, Cybersecurity, Defense-in-Depth, Denial of Service (DoS)*

Introduction and Project Goals

The main targets of dictionary attacks and credential stuffing are authentication endpoints, which are the main front doors of the internet (8). In such cases, hackers do not typically attempt to crack encryption, but rather use high-speed scripts to test thousands of common passwords until one is finally successful (9). Academic literature establishes that relying on user-generated complexity is insufficient against automated threats (12).

This project aimed to go beyond theory and construct a physical operating sandbox to see these attacks in practice. I was able to remove internet latency and test the raw CPU speed of a brute-force payload by creating both the attacking script (`attacker.py`) and the defensive server (`app.py`) on a local 127.0.0.1 network. I began with a simple, weak configuration and slowly enhanced the Python code to determine which defensive programming techniques are effective in countering the threat.

The core research question driving this simulation is: *How much does pairing a memory-hard hash function with an IP rate limiter actually slow down a brute-force script?* My hypothesis was that replacing standard $O(1)$ database lookups with Argon2id would cut the attack speed by over 99%. I expected that adding strict traffic limits would prevent this heavy cryptographic workload from causing a Denial of Service (DoS) crash on the server.

Methodology: Analyzing the Attacker Code (`attacker.py`)

To test the server, I created an Object-Oriented Python script to serve as the opponent. To maintain the implementation logic clean and modular, I decided to encapsulate the network session state and payload data with classes.

My attacker script (shown in Figure 2) is based on class inheritance. This enables the main attack logic to acquire certain TCP network characteristics of a base class, which makes the script efficient and simple to adapt to various attack situations.

Figure 1. UML Class Diagram illustrating inheritance and object encapsulation in the attacker payload

Payload Sanitization: The `load_list()` Function

The initial challenge in creating an effective attack tool is to make sure that the raw data is handled properly. Text files such as `passwords.txt` are automatically added with hidden newline characters (10). Assuming my script sent a payload of "shadow123" to the server, the database would reject it mathematically as a mismatch, even though the password itself was correct. I utilized a custom dictionary list containing 1,000 common passwords.

Listing 1: Reading and sanitizing the dictionary payload

```
1 def load_list(self):
2     '''reading the password.txt safely'''
3     try:
4         with open(self.wordlist_path, 'r', encoding='utf-8') as f:
5             # Strip() removes '\n' in the end of every password
6             self.passwords=[line.strip() for line in f.readlines()]
7             print(f"[+] Successfully loaded {len(self.passwords)} passwords.")
8     except FileNotFoundError:
9         print(f"[-] ERROR: The file {self.wordlist_path} was not found.")
```

To manage this safely, I introduced the `with open()` context manager, which makes sure that the file is closed correctly after the data has been read into memory. The fundamental reasoning is based on a list comprehension and a combination with `.strip()`. Lastly, I enclosed the logic within a `try...except` block; this will avoid the crash of the whole simulation in case the dictionary file is not found.

Execution Logic: The crack() Function

The `crack()` function is the one in which the POST requests are executed. Due to the fact that the BaseScanner parent class is initializing a `requests.Session()` object (3), the TCP connection is kept open during the attack, which essentially avoids delays in network handshakes.

Listing 2: The main brute-force loop tracking HTTP status codes

```
1 def crack(self):
2     '''the loop that finds the correct password credential'''
3     start_time=time.perf_counter()
4
5     for password in self.passwords:
6         payload={'username': self.username, 'password': password}
7         try:
8             # send the POST request over the persistent session
9             response=self.session.post(self.target_url, data=payload)
10
11            # check the http status code
12            if response.status_code==200:
13                end_time=time.perf_counter()
14                print(f"\n[!] SUCCESS: Password found: {password}")
15                print(f"[!] Time elapsed: {end_time - start_time:.2f}
16                    seconds")
17                return password
18
19            # catch the rate limiter block
20            elif response.status_code==429:
21                print(f"\n[-] FATAL: Server blocked our IP on guess: {
22                    password}")
23                print(f"[-] The attack has been stopped by the server's
24                    firewall.")
25                return None
26
27        except Exception as e:
28            print(f"[-] Connection Error: {e}")
29            return None
```

The code uses `time.perf_counter` (4) to measure the speed of execution to make the data accurate. I selected this in particular because it interacts directly with the hardware

CPU clock. Lastly, I employed a set of if/elif statements to manage the logic, such as a wrong password (401), a successful hit (200), or a rate-limit block (429).

Methodology: Building the Defense-in-Depth Server (app.py)

Built on Flask (2) and SQLite3 (1), the target server first compared input strings directly to stored values. This plain text matching ran fast - nearly one thousand checks each second by the attack tool. That speed came from constant-time lookups, labeled $O(1)$ in analysis terms. To slow down guesses, I added two separate protection stages.

Layer 1: Cryptographic Hardening with Argon2id

A secure server must make password checking hard for the computer. I imported the `argon2-cffi` library (6), which makes the function taking more memory to slow down the process (5). By setting the `memory_cost` to 65,536 and the `time_cost` to 12, I set up the system to manage hardware resources for this task.

Figure 2. The three physical architectural parameters establishing the Argon2id barrier

Each password verification now requires 12 rounds of calculation and 64 megabytes of memory. The process occurs every time when a login is attempted.

Layer 2: The Server Authentication Function

The result is that each attempt currently takes approximately half a second to complete. Protecting against potential Denial of Service (DoS) attacks caused by this heavy Argon2id verification is important, so I developed the main `authenticate()` function logic.

Listing 3: The fully secured Flask route combining Rate Limiting and Argon2id

```
1 @app.route('/auth', methods=['POST'])
2 @limiter.limit("5 per minute")
3 def authenticate():
4     username=request.form.get('username')
5     password=request.form.get('password')
6     conn=sqlite3.connect("vulnerable_vault.db")
7     cursor=conn.cursor()
8     # parameterized query to prevent SQL Injection
9     cursor.execute("SELECT pwd FROM accounts WHERE user=?", (username,))
10    result=cursor.fetchone()
11    conn.close()
12    if result:
13        db_hash=result[0]
14        try:
15            ph.verify(db_hash, password)
16            return jsonify({"access": "granted"}), 200
17        except VerifyMismatchError:
```

```

18         return jsonify({"access": "denied"}), 401
19     else:
20         return jsonify({"access": "denied"}), 404

```

This segment of the code adds the final defensive layers. Specifically, the `@limiter.limit` decorator functions as a stateful checkpoint. When failed attempts reach five within one minute, access is denied, returning an HTTP 429 message (7). Verifying the database securely required using parameterized SQL queries to prevent SQL Injection (10). Finally, `verify()` recalculates the cryptographic hash. Incorrect passwords trigger a `VerifyMismatchError`, returning an HTTP 401 response.

Results: Performance and Resource Analysis

The server’s performance significantly changed when these defense mechanisms were integrated. To test the hypothesis, I altered the `Argon2id time_cost` parameter to observe its direct effect on payload velocity. The quantitative metrics in Table 1 highlight these results.

Table 1. Comparative Analysis of Authentication Payload Efficiency

Environment Setup	Algorithm Logic	Speed (Guesses/sec)	DoS Protection
Vulnerable Baseline	Plaintext Comparison $O(1)$	≈ 850	None
Weak Hash Config	Argon2id ($t = 2, m = 65536$)	≈ 15	None
Secure Hash Config	Argon2id ($t = 12, m = 65536$)	2	None
Defense-in-Depth	Argon2id ($t = 12$) + Rate Limit	2	Blocked at 5 th attempt

In Figure 4, the defense drastically degraded the attack. Instead of guessing 850 passwords every second, the server had to work much harder. By testing a weak configuration ($t = 2$), the script managed 15 checks per second. Pushing the time cost to $t = 12$ created an architectural bottleneck that dropped the execution speed down to only 2 checks per second, validating the initial hypothesis.

Figure 3. Impact of Cryptographic Implementation on Mean Payload Velocity

To really understand the impact, I ran a quick test with the rate limiter turned off. During this test, the host machine experienced immediate 100% CPU utilization and thermal throttling (indicated by the cooling fans activating). Because Argon2id intentionally eats up 64MB of

RAM and demands 12 CPU passes per guess (5), my attack script sending hundreds of requests basically maxed out my hardware. The simulation was run on a local machine equipped with an Intel Core i7 14700HX processor and 32GB of RAM, utilizing Python 3.10 and Flask 3.0. This proved to me that while cryptography protects the passwords, it accidentally creates a huge Denial of Service (DoS) vulnerability. If I didn't add the Flask-Limiter (7), a real hacker could just crash the server by spamming fake logins.

Figure 4. The Rate Limiter Block Execution

Figure 4 shows the final defense kicking in. The script only got through five guesses before the Flask-Limiter successfully intercepted the automated requests. The `attacker.py` script got hit with a 429 status code and was forced to stop completely.

Discussion: Legacy Data Vulnerabilities

During testing, I recognized an anomaly- the attack script remained successful despite the new Argon2id implementation. Upon investigation, I realized my Python code was still reading the legacy `vulnerable_vault.db` file. Because that old file was still in my folder, the server just skipped the new hashing setup and kept comparing the old plaintext passwords. I had to manually delete the `.db` file to force the server to build a new Argon2id hashed database. This mistake showed me exactly how real companies get breached when they forget to delete old database backups or leave behind legacy files after a system migration.

Future Work

Even though this project successfully blocked a basic brute-force attack, real-world security according to NIST standards (11) is always a work in progress. In the next versions of my project, I would focus on adding:

- **Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA):** There is always a tiny chance an attacker guesses the right password on their very first try, even with rate limiting. Adding an app like Google Authenticator means a compromised password wouldn't be enough to get in.
- **Honeytokens:** I could put fake users in the database (like an account named "superadmin"). Since real users would never interact with it, the server instantly knows anyone trying to log in is a hacker. Instead of only blocking the attack at the web level, the server could push the hacker's IP to the main firewall, putting them in a temporary timeout until an administrator can review what happened.

Conclusion

Building the environment from scratch made me realize that being too fast is actually a severe vulnerability for a login page. Seeing how easily a Python `requests.Session()` script could crack the server was a demonstration of how vulnerable standard endpoints are.

Getting rid of the $O(1)$ plaintext verification and implementing `Argon2id` immediately broke the attack script's speed advantage. Attack throughput decreased from approximately 850 guesses/sec to just 2 guesses/sec, representing a reduction greater than 99% and supporting the hypothesis. However, since that kind of heavy math can easily exhaust the server's RAM, `Flask-Limiter` was added as a necessary firewall to terminate connections after five failed guesses. If there is one thing this project proved, it's that we cannot just hope users pick strong passwords. We have to actively design architectures that stall and reject malicious traffic.

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